

The Evolution of the Rule of Law: Judicial Review and the Concept of Sovereign Immunity: An Adapted Version of My Speech at Pakistan College of Law on April 25, 2024

Frederik Waage, Professor, dr. jur. wsr, University of Southern Denmark

Abstract:

This article, based on a speech delivered by the author at Pakistan College of Law on April 25, 2024, explores the evolution of the rule of law and the mechanism of judicial review across two predominant legal traditions: common law and civil law. It highlights the concept of sovereign immunity and its impact on the relationship between the state and individual rights. Drawing on historical examples from Hobbes's *Leviathan* to modern constitutional frameworks, the article underscores the significance of dismantling state immunity for the establishment of judicial accountability and the realization of fundamental human rights. This discussion is particularly relevant in the context of contemporary legal challenges and the ongoing quest for democracy and justice worldwide.

The Evolution of the Rule of Law: Judicial Review and the Concept of Sovereign Immunity:

Frederik Waage, Professor, dr. jur. wsr,
University of Southern Denmark

Lecture at Pakistan College of Law on 25 April 2024

Dear students of law,

I feel tremendously privileged to have the opportunity to address you here in Lahore. The point of my lecture today is to share my perspective on how we can summarize the evolution of the rule of law and judicial review of government decisions within the two main legal traditions: common law and civil law. My lecture centers on two main themes.

First, it is about a loss. Secondly, it is about the foundation of something new—the establishment of a whole new order of things. These themes today constitute the core of the understanding of judicial review in both the common law and civil law states, based on the rule of law.

Allow me to begin by addressing the concept of loss. More than a decade ago, as a young scholar specializing in procedural law, I traveled to the United States as part of almost six years of study regarding the role of the state in court proceedings in Denmark and other jurisdictions.

As a starting point, I became very occupied with trying to understand and define the special features of the state when it appeared in court in cases

involving judicial review and cases where the state itself was a party. Then I came across the doctrine of sovereign immunity, and suddenly everything "sort of" fell into place. In my opinion, we simply cannot understand the state, nor can we understand administrative law and constitutional law within common law and civil law, unless we investigate the concept of immunity as the fundamental starting point.

Let me explain this further. Why is immunity so important and such a dominant feature when we deal with issues of administrative law? Let us have a look at this picture.

This, dear students of law, is Hobbes's Leviathan.

Emma Laws, an English librarian, has summarized the frontispiece on the cover of his major work as follows:

"Thomas Hobbes' Leviathan from 1651 contains one of the most remarkable frontispieces of the 17th century. It was designed by Abraham Bosse, a French artist, in collaboration with the author, and is a striking representation of Hobbes' thinking on society and government. Influenced by the turmoil of the Civil War in England, Thomas Hobbes developed his theory that only a strong and absolute sovereign could sustain peace. He appropriates the sea monster of the Old Testament as a unifying sovereign of church and state. The frontispiece encapsulates Hobbes' central idea in a single image. The Leviathan—the sovereign—is a powerful crowned giant rising above the landscape, wielding both a sword (a symbol of earthly

authority) and a crosier (a symbol of ecclesiastical authority). Thomas Hobbes's social contract theory was based on the idea that individual people give up their freedoms to avoid living in a state of nature. Hobbes's view of the state of nature was one of constant competition and the threat of violence and death. Therefore, the best form of government was one of absolute monarchy."

The main headline of the picture—above Leviathan's head—states: "There is no power on earth to be compared to him."

Back in the 18th century, in Europe, Hobbes's ideas could legitimize the absolutistic state with rulers who were kings, emperors, and the like. These rulers were not democratically elected; they were normally considered warlords who kept things in order. In many countries, it was a hereditary supremacy.

What particularly shaped the autocratic forms of government that characterized Europe in the past was, firstly, that the individual played no role. The individual had surrendered his powers to the strong king. This king was above the law and could make arbitrary decisions without consequences. The king was a dictator. What is of most interest in our context here, however, is one particular characteristic: the king could not be sued. The king was simply immune from lawsuits. I guess it makes sense when you see the picture of Leviathan. He does not exactly look like a person who would happily be dragged into court and placed before a judge.

The theory of the king's immunity has characterized both common law and civil law traditions. In English law, a

distinction gradually developed between the king as a person and the king—or crown—as a concept. When the office could be separated from the person, English legal theory could also abandon the logical inference that initially legitimized the king's immunity: that the king could not be his own judge. The king or crown were legal persons, while the king as a human being was given a status vis-à-vis his officials that theoretically corresponded to the status of an incapacitated person in relation to his legal guardian. This conceptual shift allowed for a more different understanding of the scope of authority attributed to the sovereign.

In connection with this new conceptualization, the Crown's immunity from legal action could now be explained: The king can do no wrong, thus referring to a legal person. The doctrine of the sovereign's immunity took its final form in the 18th century. It was summarized by William Blackstone as a legal principle that precluded the possibility of action against the king without consent.

In the 17th century, new barriers were erected for the king and parliament through a series of special civil rights that included restrictions on immunity. The Petition of Rights of 1628 established a requirement for legal authority for taxes and protection against deprivation of liberty, just as civil liberties were reinforced by the Habeas Corpus Act of 1679 and the Bill of Rights of 1689. In English common law, similar review institutions for administrative decisions were developed.

Mandamus, prohibition, and certiorari may be highlighted here. These institutes are referred to in modern terminology as mandatory orders, prohibiting orders, and quashing orders, respectively. Citizens also obtained an early right of petition, after which they were given the opportunity to apply to the king for the right to bring proceedings against the crown in the ordinary courts. Early on, private individuals who had a contractual claim against the crown began to be given the opportunity to sue. The procedure then became that the king and parliament could refer the complaint for further legal proceedings. Consideration could be given to a committee established for this purpose, or the unresolved complaints would be referred by the king and parliament to the existing English courts for consideration.

Now let me dwell a little on the differences between common law and civil law today. One of the best contributions I have read on the subject, which I highly recommend, is John Merryman's book titled "The Civil Law Tradition." It focuses on the fact that the civil law tradition originates in Roman Law, with the great *corpus juris civilis* as a central point—a law book—while the common law tradition starts with William the Conqueror in 1066.

A number of countries in continental Europe, including Italy, France, Germany, and the Scandinavian countries, adhere to the civil law tradition, which today is largely based on written rules, legislative acts, and major legislative codifications. For us, everything revolves around the statutory act. For those of us who are civil

law lawyers, this means that all interpretation of the law starts with the text of the law itself. In some civil law countries, the history of the statutory act, which means the draft of the act, what in French is called *travaux préparatoires*,* also plays a significant role.

That is why some call the interpretation of civil law legislation the interpretation of frozen or solidified politics. We try to get into the minds of the people who adopted the act—or rather, at least in Denmark, into the minds of the civil servants who wrote the act that passed through parliament

Therefore, the most important task for those of us who are civil law lawyers is to be detectives of truth. We need to find out what the legislator meant when the legislator passed the legislative act at issue. This can be accomplished because we have excellent records and archives of legislative proposals from our parliament.

Common law, on the other hand, can be seen as diametrically opposed to civil law. Now students, you are the experts here. In common law, the starting point is judge-made law. Common law is based on custom, and although legislative acts or statutes also play an important role in the United Kingdom, the United States, Australia, India, and Pakistan, the difference is that the world does not revolve around the legislative act in common law.

But back to square one. Both in common law and civil law, the king's immunity from legal action has historically been emphasized. The history of the waiver of

the immunity of state power – the loss of immunity – is, therefore, the history of the establishment of what we understand as the modern rule of law.

The French Declaration of the Rights of Man and of the Citizen of 1789 identified some core human rights, including freedom of religion, freedom of speech, and the inviolability of property rights. These rights can be seen as a major blow to the power of Leviathan. Freedom of speech and freedom of assembly, for instance, represent freedoms from interference by the king.

With the establishment of human rights, we obtained the first fundamental building block for the establishment of the rule of law on the continent. As mentioned earlier, in England, where the cooperation between king and parliament became profound after the Glorious Revolution, rights such as habeas corpus were recognized much earlier. Around the same time as the French Revolution in the United States, the first ten amendments to the Constitution – known as the American Bill of Rights – were passed, containing a number of corresponding rights that safeguard the citizen.

This laid the foundation for cases concerning the control of administrative decisions taken by the state and for cases concerning the liability of the state. In conclusion, the current state based on the rule of law was created upon the ruins of sovereign immunity. It was based on a loss.

While there was a common understanding that immunity had to be relinquished, there was no consensus on the type of judicial control to which Leviathan should be subject. I continue to use the Leviathan analogy here because, in the early years following the adoption of modern constitutions in 19th century Europe, immunity was not entirely abolished. Rather, we observe many years of development of judicial review in different jurisdictions. In fact, remnants of immunity still exist today in both common law and civil law countries.

For instance, in the United States, although it is a republic, there remains an adherence to Blackstone's famous line: "The King can do no wrong." This means that, as a starting point, one cannot sue the American state. Even today, suing the American state requires a waiver – a legislative act that permits such actions. This waiver may be found at the constitutional level or through legislative acts enacted by Congress. For example, the Federal Tort Claims Act has gradually introduced more provisions under which the state can be sued.

Now, why do states retain elements of immunity? The main reason is that it addresses an obvious problem faced by the state in court. As we have already discussed, citizens are granted a number of human rights, including the right to privacy and the right to freedom of expression. On the other hand, traditionally, the state or government has not been granted any rights. Human rights do not apply to states! In the legal order, this problem has been resolved by

allowing the state to retain certain elements of the immunity that once belonged to the king. The different elements of immunity that are preserved are, so to speak, the human rights of the state.

For example, in any jurisdiction, it may not be possible to compel the state to disclose state secrets in court. This is an element of immunity retained to secure balance in the process. Additionally, in many countries, while it may be possible to take the state to court, there might be very short time limits for doing so. Legislation may require that a complaint be filed within a fortnight or within three months; after that, the state's immunity is restored, and the citizen can no longer sue.

But which courts should handle the new cases involving judicial review of the state? In the German states, there was considerable debate among legal scholars about how judicial review should proceed now that state immunity had been dissolved. German jurisprudence focused its efforts on creating the ideal constitutional state. The ideal image, referred to as a "State of Law" or Rechtsstaat, was envisioned as "a system of rules created by academic experts with the aim of eliminating all forms of arbitrary exercise of power."+

The constitutional state that was developed is still a model for Germany. After extensive debate, a solution was reached by establishing special administrative courts, partly inspired by the French Conseil d'État, an institution established by Napoleon in 1799.

Administrative courts differ from the courts we know in the common law world because they are typically specialized courts. This contrasts with the ordinary courts in the United Kingdom and the United States, which are generalist courts. Administrative courts do not use an adversarial system in the same manner as other courts. In administrative courts, it is the judge who is responsible for investigating the case. A key idea is that the citizen should be able to go to court without a lawyer. This is possible because the judge—not an attorney—is responsible for investigating the case.

Another feature that characterizes administrative courts is their proximity to government decisions compared to other types of courts. For instance, during the COVID-19 pandemic in Germany, Berlin chose to close bars and restaurants early in the evening to slow the spread of infection. The restaurants exercised their constitutional right to challenge the early evening closure before an administrative court in Berlin, reaching a decision within a few days. In that instance, the court found that the measure was disproportionate. Consequently, immediately, the Berlin bars and restaurants were allowed to reopen.

German administrative courts are also known for operating with so-called interim measures, where the court temporarily suspends a government decision to a much greater extent than is common in many other countries.

In Denmark, my home country, we do not have administrative courts, and there is no strong tradition of court intervention in

governance. We rarely use interim measures. It is evident that there is a significant difference between a court decision that is backward-looking—where, for example, the state must pay compensation several years after the events have transpired—and a court actually interfering in ongoing activities.

In Denmark, for various reasons, it was decided not to establish specialized courts. Therefore, we apply the same procedural rules for disputes against the state as we do for disputes between private parties.

So how does this work in practice? We do not have a writ of mandamus, nor do we have a certiorari system. Instead, a citizen hires their own attorney, and the state hires its own attorney. Regardless of whether the case concerns human rights, the two parties will contest in court following the same procedural rules as those applicable to private parties. The biggest law firm in Denmark is a private law firm that represents the state, and in these cases, the judge simply plays the role of a referee.

If I were to highlight one important legal concept that is at the heart of the constitutional state, it would have to be the principle of legality. As we understand the principle in Danish law, it includes, first and foremost, the requirement of a legal basis. To interfere with the legal rights of citizens—using legal terms—requires a legal basis.

The principle of legality is most evident in criminal law, where the fundamental rule in Latin is *nulla poena sine lege*: "no punishment without the law." The state

may not punish a citizen unless there is a clear legal basis for doing so—in practice, this is provision in a legislative act. For citizens, this therefore means that everything that is not forbidden is allowed. Conversely, for the state, it means that everything the state is not explicitly permitted to do to a citizen is forbidden.

What, then, is the link between this requirement for a legal basis and democracy? The answer to that question is straightforward: Parliament makes the law, and Parliament provides the Government with the power or legal basis to act in a given area.

Let me conclude by returning to the starting point. In this lecture, I addressed two main themes: first, the loss we experienced—where we all came from, namely sovereign immunity. Secondly, after that immunity was relinquished, a new system of rules was established. However, we still retain elements of immunity. The powerful Leviathan continues to play a significant role in the background concerning matters of immunity.

Through this discussion, it becomes clear that although the path toward the modern rule of law has been marked by significant losses and transformations, the legacy of the sovereign continues to shape our legal frameworks. Understanding these historical underpinnings is vital as we navigate contemporary legal issues and seek to balance the state's power with the protection of individual rights in an ever-evolving legal landscape.

*Travaux préparatoires refers to the preparatory work related to legislative acts, which serves as crucial guidance in interpreting legal texts. This historical context adds to our understanding of civil law traditions and aids in interpreting the intent behind the enacted legislation.

+Martina Künnecke, Tradition and change in Administrative Law - an Anglo-German comparison, p. side 23).